

INFUSION METHOD IN MICRO CELL PATHY SYSTEM OF MEDICINE FOR IMPROVING SEVEN PATHOLOGICAL CONDITIONS

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ABSTRACT

The present invention relates to a method for improving seven pathological conditions by the infusion method. The present invention includes an infusion method involving micro cell pathy for improving gangrene and cancer. The present invention includes a process for the manufacturing of Microcell pathy pills using the odic tincture. The manufacturing of Microcell pathy globules by odic tincture is used for the treatment of seven pathology conditions. The Microcell pathy method is used for the treatment of seven pathology conditions. The seven pathology conditions are stagnation, inflammation, pains and numbness, positive and negative fever, suppuration (growth of tumors), gangrene, and cancer.

FIELD OF THE INVENTION

The present invention relates to an infusion method for improving seven pathological conditions and more specifically, relates to a method of developing micro cell pathy pills to treat organ condition, gangrene, and cancer.

BACKGROUND OF THE INVENTION

With the increase in population, unhealthy life and polluted environment diseases are also increased with optimum level. People are suffering from different diseases on daily basis and to cure themselves they are taking much medicine present in the market which is generally

synthetic drugs. Synthetic drugs are designed to mimic organic botanical compounds, but they often contain highly processed chemicals. The body has difficulty recognizing synthetic drugs, which makes them harder to process and metabolize. For this reason, these drugs are more likely to induce toxicity and adverse side effects. The pharmaceutical industry faced challenges to derive medicine from natural sources. The best treatment for today's generation comes from natural sources for example plants, microbes, and worms, which can help to reduce the side effects. Infusion on the other hand is a chemical process that uses botanicals (typically dried herbs, flowers, or berries) that are volatile and release their active ingredients readily in water, oil, or alcohol. In this process, a liquid is typically boiled (or brought to another appropriate temperature) and poured over the herb. After the herb has been allowed to steep in the liquid for an appropriate period, it is removed (possibly by straining) leaving an infusion. Unless the infusion is to be consumed immediately, it is bottled and refrigerated for future use. The amount of time the herbs are left in the liquid depends on the kind of infusion. Infusion times can range from seconds (for some kinds of Chinese tea) to hours, days, or months (for liqueurs like Sloe Gin).

There are several accessories and techniques for removing the steeped or leftover botanicals that were used to infuse liquids, including metal steepers (which look like clamps), tea infusers (which act as strainers), and french presses (which are commonly used to infuse water with various teas and coffee). The most commonly used technique is teabag, which is made with filter paper and filled with various tea flavors. There are inherited challenges faced by homeopathy which are not able to produce the desired results. In the last few years, the tumor mechanism has been studied and the mechanisms underlying the tumor progression have been explained little by little. Thus, during the tumor progression, the cancer cells leave the primary tumor, pass through the vascular membranes and migrate into the surrounding extracellular matrix. These phenomena together involve the secretion, then the activation, of proteolytic enzymes, such as the plasminogen activation system. The expression profile of these proteolytic enzymes, studied in various cell lines of human or mouse melanoma, reveals a very strong increase in the expression of various MMPs, in a manner correlated with the invasive phenotype of these cells.

US20130079416A1 discloses a homeopathic medicament that relates to a composition comprising phenacetin, in particular a Phenacetinu 4CH homeopathic medicament for use in the treatment of cancer.

DE10108676 discloses a homeopathic medicament (I) is derived from seeds of the hemp plant *Cannabis sativa*. (I) is prepared by a spagyric method.

The present invention is an advancement of already existing methods in this field of invention. The drawbacks of already existing systems are that all the already existing inventions are less efficient and can improve one or two pathological conditions and are not easily reproducible which affects the survival of the patient. The present invention also involves producing purified, natural medicine that is easily assimilated. The present invention involves improving seven pathological conditions including cancer and gangrene. None of the existing technology uses such a method that is disclosed in the present invention. The present invention effectively overcomes the deficiencies in the prior art. Hence there is a need for the present invention.

OBJECTIVE OF THE INVENTION

The main objective of the present invention is an infusion method for improving seven pathology conditions.

Another objective of the present invention is to provide improvement for stagnation.

Yet another objective of the present invention is to provide improvement for inflammation.

Yet another objective of the present invention is to provide improvement for pains.

Yet another objective of the present invention is to provide improvement for numbness.

Yet another objective of the present invention is to provide improvement for positive and negative fever.

Yet another objective of the present invention is to provide improvement for suppuration.

Yet another objective of the present invention is to provide improvement for gangrene.

Yet another objective of the present invention is to provide improvement for cancer.

Yet another objective of the present invention is to provide plant oriented infusion method to develop micro cell pathy pills.

Further objectives, advantages, and features of the present invention will become apparent from the detailed description provided hereinbelow, in which various embodiments of the disclosed invention are illustrated by way of example and appropriate reference to accompanying drawings.

SUMMARY OF THE PRESENT INVENTION

The present invention relates to a method for improving seven pathology conditions, includes an infusion method involving micro cell pathy. The method includes a ground herb. The ground herb is extracted and is shade-dried. The extracted ground herbs are made in powder form by using a mixture grinder. The powder form of the ground herbs is kept in a mud pot. Herein, the mud pot contains 100g of powdered ground herb with 500ml of water and 10 ml of honey, resulting in a mixture. The mixture is then extracted into two parts an organic compound and an inorganic compound. The organic compounds of the ground herb are broken down from complex substances to simple primary metabolites and these primary metabolites are further broken down to secondary metabolites. The inorganic compounds of the ground herb are shade dried and are burned in a muffle furnace at 600⁰C, and the organic and the inorganic compounds of the ground herb are kept for 7 days at room temperature, and resulting in the formation of the crude odic tincture. Herein, the organic compounds of the ground herbs include protein, carbohydrates, fat, and nucleic acid. In the preferred embodiment, the seven pathology conditions include stagnation, inflammation, pains and numbness, fever (positive and negative), suppuration (growth of tumors), gangrene, and cancer. In an aspect of the invention, the primary metabolites(macronutrient) of the ground herb includes amino acid, glucose, fatty acid glycerol, nucleotides in which glucose goes to further broke down and produced ethanol. In an aspect of the invention, the secondary metabolites of the ground herbs include alkaloids, flavonoids, resins tannin, and pigments. Herein, the trace elements and secondary metabolites of the ground herb vary from plant to plant (residue of inorganic substances). In an embodiment of the invention, the method for the formation of globules from crude odic tincture includes, 1 part of crude odic tincture of the ground herb is mix with 5 part of the rectified spirit that gave an OT1 solution. 1 part of the OT1 solution mix with 5 part of the rectified spirit that gave an OT2 solution. 1 part of the OT2 solution mix with 5 part of the rectified spirit that gave an OT3 solution and the OT3 solution is used for making globules. In another aspect of the invention, the two forces acting on the OT3 solution for the formation of globules are cohesive force and adhesive force that act intermolecularly and intra-molecularly respectively. In an embodiment of the invention,

the seven pathology conditions are treated by using the Micro cell pathy method. The method includes the first dilution of 1 Microcell pathy Pill in 120 ml of water in the first glass for the treatment of the first disease condition. The second dilution includes the transfer of 1 tablespoon from the first glass to the second glass for the treatment of a second disease condition. The third dilution includes the transfer of 1 tablespoon from the second glass to the third glass for the treatment of the third disease condition (pains and numbness). The fourth dilution includes the transfer of 1 tablespoon from the third glass to the fourth glass for the treatment of the fourth disease condition. The fifth dilution includes the transfer of 1 tablespoon from the fourth glass to the fifth glass for the treatment of the fifth disease condition.

One advantage of the present invention is that the present invention improves stagnation.

Another advantage of the present invention is that the present invention is used to provide improvement in inflammation.

Yet another advantage of the present invention is that the present invention provides an improvement in pain.

Yet another advantage of the present invention is that the present invention provides an improvement in numbness.

Yet another advantage of the present invention is that the present invention provides an improvement in positive and negative fever.

Yet another advantage of the present invention is that the present invention provides an improvement in suppuration.

Yet another advantage of the present invention is that the present invention provides an improvement in gangrene.

Yet another advantage of the present invention is that the present invention provides an improvement in cancer.

DETAILED DESCRIPTION OF THE INVENTION

While this invention is susceptible to embodiment in many different forms, there is shown in the drawings and will herein be described in detail specific embodiments, with the

understanding that the present disclosure of such embodiments is to be considered as an example of the principles and not intended to limit the invention to the specific embodiments shown and described. In the description below, reference numerals are used to describe the same, similar, or corresponding parts in the several views of the drawings. This detailed description defines the meaning of the terms used herein and specifically describes embodiments for those skilled in the art to practice the invention.

Definition

The terms “a” or “an”, as used herein, are defined as one or as more than one. The term “plurality”, as used herein, is defined as two or as more than two. The term “another”, as used herein, is defined as at least a second or more. The terms “including” and/or “having”, as used herein, are defined as comprising (i.e., open language). The term “coupled”, as used herein, is defined as connected, although not necessarily directly, and not necessarily mechanically.

The term “comprising” is not intended to limit inventions to only claiming the present invention with such comprising language. Any invention using the term comprising could be separated into one or more claims using “consisting” or “consisting of” claim language and is so intended. The term “comprising” is used interchangeably used by the terms “having” or “containing”.

Reference throughout this document to “one embodiment”, “certain embodiments”, “an embodiment”, “another embodiment”, and “yet another embodiment” or similar terms means that a particular feature, structure, or characteristic described in connection with the embodiment is included in at least one embodiment of the present invention. Thus, the Appearances of such phrases or in various places throughout this specification are not necessarily all referring to the same embodiment. Furthermore, the particular features, structures, or characteristics are combined in any suitable manner in one or more embodiments without limitation.

The term “or” as used herein is to be interpreted as an inclusive or meaning any one or any combination. Therefore, “A, B or C” means any of the following: “A; B; C; A and B; A and C; B and C; A, B and C”. An exception to this definition will occur only when a combination of elements, functions, steps or acts are in some way inherently mutually exclusive.

As used herein, the term "one or more" generally refers to, but is not limited to, singular as well as plural form of the term.

The drawings featured in the figures are to illustrate certain convenient embodiments of the present invention and are not to be considered as limitations thereto. The term "means" preceding a present participle of an operation indicates the desired function for which there is one or more embodiments, i.e., one or more methods, devices, or apparatuses for achieving the desired function and that one skilled in the art could select from these or their equivalent is given the disclosure herein and use of the term "means" is not intended to be limiting.

The present invention relates to a method for improving seven pathology conditions, includes an infusion method involving micro cell pathy. The method includes a ground herb. The ground herb is extracted and is shade-dried. The extracted ground herbs are made in powder form by using a mixture grinder. The powder form of the ground herbs is kept in a mud pot. Herein, the mud pot contains 100g of powdered ground herb with 500ml of water and 10 ml of honey, resulting in a mixture. The mixture is then extracted into two parts an organic compound and an inorganic compound. The organic compounds of the ground herb are broken down from complex substances to simple primary metabolites and these primary metabolites are further broken down to secondary metabolites. The inorganic compounds of the ground herb are shade dried and are burned in a muffle furnace at 600⁰C, and the organic and the inorganic compounds of the ground herb are kept for 7 days at room temperature, and resulting in the formation of the crude odic tincture. Herein, the organic compounds of the ground herb include protein, carbohydrates, fat, and nucleic acid.

In the preferred embodiment, the seven pathology conditions include stagnation, inflammation, pains and numbness, fever (positive and negative), suppuration (growth of tumors), gangrene, and cancer. In an aspect of the invention, the primary metabolites(macronutrient) of the ground herb includes amino acid, glucose, fatty acid glycerol, nucleotides in which glucose goes to further broke down and produced ethanol. In an aspect of the invention, the secondary metabolites of the ground herb include alkaloids, flavonoids, resins tannin, and pigments. Herein, the trace elements and secondary metabolites of the ground herb vary from plant to plant (residue of inorganic substances).

In an embodiment of the invention, the method for the formation of globules from crude odic tincture includes, 1 part of crude odic tincture of the ground herb is mix with 5 part of the

rectified spirit that gave an OT1 solution. 1 part of the OT1 solution mix with 5 part of the rectified spirit that gave an OT2 solution. 1 part of the OT2 solution mix with 5 part of the rectified spirit that gave an OT3 solution and the OT3 solution is used for making globules.

In another aspect of the invention, the two forces acting on the OT3 solution for the formation of globules are cohesive force and adhesive force that act intermolecularly and intra-molecularly respectively.

In an embodiment of the invention, the seven pathology conditions are treated by using the Micro cell pathy method. The method includes the first dilution of 1 Microcell pathy Pill in 120 ml of water in the first glass for the treatment of the first disease condition. The second dilution includes the transfer of 1 tablespoon from the first glass to the second glass for the treatment of a second disease condition. The third dilution includes the transfer of 1 tablespoon from the second glass to the third glass for the treatment of the third disease condition (pains and numbness). The fourth dilution includes the transfer of 1 tablespoon from the third glass to the fourth glass for the treatment of the fourth disease condition. The fifth dilution includes the transfer of 1 tablespoon from the fourth glass to the fifth glass for the treatment of the fifth disease condition.

The present invention relates to a method for improving seven pathology conditions, includes an infusion method involving micro cell pathy. The method includes a one or more ground herbs. The one or more ground herb is extracted and is shade-dried. The extracted one or more ground herbs are made in powder form by using a mixture grinder. The powder form of the one or more ground herbs is kept in a mud pot. Herein, the mud pot contains 100g of powdered the one or more ground herbs with 500ml of water and 10 ml of honey, resulting in a mixture.

The mixture is then extracted into two parts an organic compound and an inorganic compound.

The organic compounds of the one or more ground herbs are broken down from complex substances to simple primary metabolites and these primary metabolites are further broken down to secondary metabolites. The inorganic compounds of the one or more ground herbs are shade dried and are burned in a muffle furnace at 600⁰C, and the organic and the inorganic compounds of the one or more ground herbs are kept for 7 days at room

temperature, and resulting in the formation of the crude odic tincture. Herein, the organic compounds of the one or more ground herbs include protein, carbohydrates, fat, and nucleic acid.

In the preferred embodiment, the seven pathology conditions include stagnation, inflammation, pains and numbness, fever (positive and negative), suppuration (growth of tumors), gangrene, and cancer. In an aspect of the invention, the primary metabolites (macro nutrient) of the one or more ground herb includes amino acid, glucose, fatty acid glycerol, nucleotides in which glucose goes to further broke down and produced ethanol. In an aspect of the invention, the secondary metabolites of the one or more ground herbs include alkaloids, flavonoids, resins tannin, and pigments. Herein, the trace elements and secondary metabolites of the one or more ground herb vary from plant to plant (residue of inorganic substances).

In an embodiment of the invention, the method for the formation of globules from crude odic tincture includes, 1 part of crude odic tincture of the one or more ground herb is mix with 5 part of the rectified spirit that gave an OT1 solution. 1 part of the OT1 solution mix with 5 part of the rectified spirit that gave an OT2 solution. 1 part of the OT2 solution mix with 5 part of the rectified spirit that gave an OT3 solution, and the OT3 solution is used for making globules

In another aspect of the invention, the two forces acting on the OT3 solution for the formation of globules are cohesive force and adhesive force that act intermolecularly and intra-molecularly respectively.

In an embodiment of the invention, the seven pathology conditions are treated by using the Micro cell pathy method. The method includes the first dilution of 1 Microcell pathy Pill in 120 ml of water in the first glass for the treatment of the first disease condition. The second dilution includes the transfer of 1 tablespoon from the first glass to the second glass for the treatment of a second disease condition. The third dilution includes the transfer of 1 tablespoon from the second glass to the third glass for the treatment of the third disease condition (pains and numbness). The fourth dilution includes the transfer of 1 tablespoon from the third glass to the fourth glass for the treatment of the fourth disease condition. The fifth dilution includes the transfer of 1 tablespoon from the fourth glass to the fifth glass for the treatment of the fifth disease condition.

In another embodiment, the seven pathology conditions include stagnation, inflammation, pains and numbness, fever (positive and negative), suppuration (growth of tumors), gangrene, and cancer. In the preferred embodiment, the infusion method is a chemical process that uses botanicals (typically dried herbs, flowers, or berries) that are volatile and release their active ingredients readily in water, oil, or alcohol. The active release of the volatile compound is performed by boiling the herb or brought the herbs to another appropriate temperature. After the herb has been allowed to steep in the liquid for an appropriate period, it is removed (possibly by straining) leaving an infusion. Unless the infusion is to be consumed immediately, it is bottled and refrigerated for future use. In the preferred embodiment, all medicines are made from the essence of the plants. In the preferred embodiment, “process of odic tincher” generally refers to but the method of extracting the essence of the plants, which is the vital energy of plants that store in them and has a powerful capacity to cure the disease. In the preferred embodiment, the term “ground herb” generally refers to the medicinal plants used as traditional medicine practices since prehistoric times.

In the preferred embodiment, ground herbs required for infusion method are *Cochlearia officinalis*, *Hydras candensis*, *Nasturtium officinale*, *Smilax medica*, *Scrophularia aquatic*, *Tussilagofarfar*, *Veronica becabunga*, *Anchusa officinalis*, *Avenastiva*, *Malvasylvestes*, *Sanguinaria Canadensis*, *Aesculushippocastanum*, *Berberis vulgaris*, *Cetria centare*, *Cetria islandica*, *Cinchona calisaya*, *Cinchona rubra*, *Salix alba*, *Syringavulgaaris*, *Chironia centapium*, *Chironia chilensis*, *Humulus lupulus*, *Menyanthes trifoliata*, *Oxalis coniculata*, *Simaruba amara*, *Adiantum capillus veneris*, *Cardocynara*, *Ipecacunha officinalis*, *Melilotus officinalis*, *Phelanium aquaticum*, *Polygala vulgaris*, *Scolopendrium officinalis*, *Althea officinalis*, *Betula alnus*, *Dieruilletourneforti*, *Eucalyptus globules*, *Lythrum salicaria*, *Myrtus communis*, *Physalis alkekengi*, *Populus alba*, *Rosa canina*, *Solanum dulcamara*, *Sorbus aucuparia*, *Steffensia elongate*, *Tilia europae*, *Veronia officinalis*, *Viburnum prunifolium*, *Vinca major*, *Allium sativum*, *Carthamus lanatus*, *Chenopodium vulgare*, *Dicatanum albas*, *Euphorbia officinalis*, *Rutagraveolens*, *Euonymus atropurpureus*, *Hura crepitans*, *Mercurialis annua*, *Momordica elaterium*, *Orobancha major*, *Podophyllum peltatum*, *Polygonatum vulgare*, *Asclepias gigantea*, *Conium maculatum*, *Pimpinella magna*, *Rhus radicans*, *Rhus toxicodendron*, *Achillea millefolium*, *Anthemis nobilis*, *Apium petroselinum*, *Cicaria tinum*, *Cynara scolymus*, *Genista scoparia*, *Gulacum officinalis*, *Leontodon taraxacum*, *Rutagraveolens*, *Sanguisorba officinalis*, *Sorbus aucuparia*, *Taxus baccata*, *Triticum sativum*, *Arnica montana*, *Pinus sigra*,

Teraxacumleontodon, ScrophulariaNodosa, Evonymuseuropeaus, Smilax medica, Vinca minor, Azadirachtaindica.

In the preferred embodiment, the term “Odic tincture” generally refers to but is not limited to ‘tincture’. The tincture is a trace or indication that reveals the presence of something. In pharmacology, a tincture is a type of medicine extracted from a plant in an alcohol solution. There are many meanings to the word tincture, but most of them involve something that leaves a trace or residue. It is our experience that every disease consists of the distemper of the Odic forces (the so-called "Fluid of life") in our organism. The Odic forces of our remedies remove this distemper according to the laid of similarity, that is, in the manner in which our remedies when in crude form, are capable of calling forth the disease. Tinctures are liquid extracts made from herbs that you take orally (by mouth). They are usually extracted in alcohol but they can also be extracted in vegetable glycerin or apple cider vinegar (non-alcohol). Tinctures are easy and convenient to use. In the preferred embodiment, the term “rectified spirit” generally refers to known as neutral spirits, rectified alcohol, and ethyl alcohol of agricultural origin is highly concentrated ethanol that is used in purified and repeated distillation, process is called rectification. In the preferred embodiment, the term “cohesive force” generally refers to cohesive and adhesive forces are associated with bulk (or macroscopic) properties and when a liquid comes into contact with a surface (such as the walls of a graduated cylinder or a tabletop), both cohesive and adhesive forces will act on it. These forces govern the shape which the liquid takes on. Due to the effects of adhesive forces, liquid on a surface can spread out to form a thin, relatively uniform film over the surface, a process known as wetting. Alternatively, in the presence of strong cohesive forces, the liquid can divide into several small, roughly spherical beads which stand on the surface, maintaining minimal contact with the surface. Cohesive forces are the intermolecular forces that cause a tendency in liquids to resist separation. These attractive forces exist between molecules of the same substance. For instance, rain falls in droplets, rather than a fine mist, because water has strong cohesion which pulls its molecules tightly together, forming droplets. This force tends to unite molecules of a liquid, gathering them into relatively large clusters due to the molecules, dislike for its surrounding. As used herein, the term “adhesive force” generally refers to adhesive forces are the attractive forces between unlike molecules. They are caused by forces acting between two substances, such as mechanical forces (sticking together) and electrostatic forces (attraction due to opposing charges). In the case of a liquid wetting agent, adhesion causes the liquid to cling to the

surface on which it rests. When water is poured on clean glass, it tends to spread, forming a thin, uniform film over the glass surface as there are adhesive forces between water and glass which are strong enough to pull the water molecules out of their spherical formation and hold them against the surface of the glass, thus avoiding the repulsion between like molecules. When a liquid is placed on a smooth surface, the relative strengths of the cohesive and adhesive forces acting on that liquid determine the shape it will take. If the adhesive forces between a liquid and a surface are stronger, they will pull the liquid down, causing it to wet the surface. However, if the cohesive forces among the liquid itself are stronger, they will resist such adhesion and cause the liquid to retain a spherical shape and bead the surface. This determines the macroscopic effects of cohesive and adhesive forces. In the preferred embodiment, "MICRO CELL PATHY". It consists of 3 words MICRO, which means micro and macro trace elements, potential chemical energy, presence of phenolic compounds, (organic & Inorganic constituent of plants) strong antioxidant properties present in microform in medicinal plants, protect cells against oxidative damage caused by free radicals and give strength to Immune cells. **CELL:-** Cell is the basic structural and functional unit of life and biological unit of all living organism, and **PATHY:-** Means a way of treatment micro cell pathy is a natural plants potential chemical energy (organic & Inorganic constituent of plants) and strong antioxidants based pathy which give strength to our Immune cells and all body cells when we take it in microdose, ultimately diseased body restore their normal cellular function when it gives to the sick person in microdose. In the preferred embodiment, the term "stagnation" generally refers to major causes of all illness. Stagnation arises when there is "too much" of something in a particular area for some reason cause poor circulation, lack of movement, over-eating, bad diet, and all types of stress. In the preferred embodiment, the term "inflammation" generally refers to a localized physical condition in which part of the body becomes reddened, swollen, hot, and often painful, especially as a reaction to injury or infection. In the preferred embodiment, "pains" generally refer to an unpleasant sensation that can range from mild, localized discomfort to agony. In the preferred embodiment, the term "fever" generally refers to consider as any body temperature above the normal 37 C. Fever is the result of an immune response by your body to a foreign invader. The foreign invaders include viruses, bacteria, fungi, drugs, or other toxins. In the preferred embodiment, the term "numbness" generally refers to unusual prickling sensations that can happen in any part of your body. In the preferred embodiment, the term "gangrene" generally refers to a type of tissue death caused by a lack of blood supply. Symptoms of gangrene include a change in skin color to red or black, numbness,

swelling, pain, skin breakdown, and coolness. The feet and hands are the most affected area. In the preferred embodiment, the term “cancer” generally refers to a group of diseases involving abnormal cell growth with the potential to invade or spread to other parts of the body.

Further objectives, advantages, and features of the present invention will become apparent from the detailed description provided hereinbelow, in which various embodiments of the disclosed present invention are illustrated by way of example and appropriate reference to accompanying drawings. Those skilled in the art to which the present invention pertains may make modifications resulting in other embodiments employing principles of the present invention without departing from its spirit or characteristics, particularly upon considering the foregoing teachings. Accordingly, the described embodiments are to be considered in all respects only as illustrative, and not restrictive, and the scope of the present invention is, therefore, indicated by the appended claims rather than by the foregoing description or drawings. Consequently, while the present invention has been described with reference to particular embodiments, modifications of structure, sequence, materials and the like apparent to those skilled in the art still fall within the scope of the invention as claimed by the applicant.

CLAIMS

1. A method for improving seven pathology conditions, comprising: an infusion method involving micro cell pathy, the method includes an at least one ground herb;

the at least one ground herb is extracted and are shade dried;

the at least one ground herb is made in powder form by using a mixture grinder;

the powder form of the at least one ground herb is kept in a mud pot, the mud pot contains 100g of powdered ground herb with 500ml of water and 10 ml of honey, resulting in a mixture;

the mixture is then extracted into two parts an organic compound and an inorganic compound;

the organic compounds of the at least one ground herb are broken down from complex substances to simple primary metabolites and these primary metabolites are further broken

down to secondary metabolites;

the inorganic compounds of the at least one ground herb are shade dried and are burned around 600°C in a muffle furnace; and

the organic and the inorganic compounds of the at least one ground herb are kept for 7 days in room temperature, and resulting in the formation of crude odic tincture.

Wherein, the organic compounds of the at least one ground herb includes protein, carbohydrates, fat, and nucleic acid.

2. As claimed in claim 1, seven pathology conditions include stagnation, inflammation, pains and numbness, fever (positive and negative), suppuration (growth of tumors), gangrene and cancer.
3. As claimed in claim 1, wherein the primary metabolites(macro nutrient) of the at least one ground herb includes amino acid, glucose, fatty acid glycerol, nucleotides in which glucose goes to further broke down and produced ethanol.
4. As claimed in claim 1, wherein the secondary metabolites of the at least one ground herb includes alkaloids, flavonoids, resins tannin and pigments.
5. As claimed in claim 1, wherein trace elements and secondary metabolites of the at least one medicinal plants varies from plant to plants (residue of inorganic substances).
6. The method for the formation of globules from crude odic tincture, the method includes:
1 part of crude odic tincture of the at least one ground herb is mix with 5 part of rectified spirit that gave a OT1 solution;
1 part of the OT1 solution mix with 5 part of rectified spirit that gave a OT2 solution;
1 part of the OT2 solution mix with 5 part of rectified spirit that gave a OT3 solution; and
the OT3 solution is used for making globules
7. As claimed in claim 6, the two forces acting on the OT3 solution for the formation of globules are cohesive force and adhesive force that act inter molecularly and intra-molecularly respectively.
8. As claimed in claim 2, the seven pathology conditions are treated by using Micro cell

pathy method, the method comprising:

first dilution includes 1 Micro cell pathy Pill diluted in 120 ml of water in first glass for the treatment of first disease condition;

second dilution includes transfer of 1 table spoon from first glass to second glass for the treatment of second disease condition;

third dilution includes transfer of 1 table spoon from second glass to third glass for the treatment of third disease condition (pains and numbness);

fourth dilution includes transfer of 1 table spoon from third glass to fourth glass for the treatment of fourth disease condition;

fifth dilution includes transfer of 1 table spoon from fourth glass to fifth glass for the treatment of fifth disease condition;

sixth dilution includes transfer of 1 table spoon from fifth glass to sixth glass for the treatment of sixth disease condition; and

seventh dilution includes transfer of 1 table spoon from sixth glass to seven glasses for the treatment of seventh disease condition.

9. As claimed in claim 8, first disease condition includes stagnation, second disease condition includes inflammation, third disease condition includes pains and numbness, fourth disease condition includes positive and negative fever, fifth disease condition includes suppuration, sixth disease condition includes gangrene, and seventh disease condition includes cancer.

WHAT IS “MICRO CELL PATHY”?

‘MICRO CELL PATHY’ consist of three words

MICRO: Means micro and macro trace elements, potential chemical energy, presence of phenolic compounds, (organic & In-organic constituent of plants) strong antioxidant properties present in micro form in medicinal plants, protect cells against oxidative damage caused by free radicals and give strength to Immune cells.

CELL: Cell is basic structural and functional unit of life and biological unit of all living organism.

PATHY: Means a way of treatment micro cell pathy is a natural plants potential chemical energy (organic & In-organic constituent of plants) and strong antioxidants based pathy which give strength to our Immune cells and all body cells when we take it in micro dose. Ultimately, diseased body restore their normal cellular function again when it given to sick person in micro dose.

It founded by Dr. P K Das in 2017 at India after deep study of Homeopathy, Ayurveda, Naturopathy and all alternative medicines.

HOW IT WORK?

We extract various chemicals from plant and formulate in the form of medicine in microcellpathy. These works may work by diferent ways depending on their composition. Their mechanism is not scelntifically proved but we can make assumptions of their functioning. After metabolizing inside body they may function by diferent ways.

1. They may inhibit the activity of enzyme which is essential for metabolic processes as result process will be stopped so they may kllthe pathogen by inhibiting its eetabolic processes essential for survival.
2. Some medicine may degrade cell wall of pathogens and disturb their esmotic balance as result pathogen dies.
3. Some medicine may reduce formation of free radicals generated by oxidative stress resultingantiaging4 Some may Induce the fomation of mmune cells and increase their abilty to fight with pathogens.

Medicinal use of secondary metabolites of plants in Cell & Cellular Metabolism

Plant produces several secondary metabolites like alkaloids, terpenoids, pigments, phenolic compounds, lectins etc. some are used for medicinal purposes. These compounds show different mode of action: some kill pathogen by stopping their metabolic process or by breaking cell wall.

All the chemical reactions that takes place inside cell is called metabolism. It le of two types- anabolism & catabolism. Chemical reactions in which small molecules combine to form large molecule is called as catabolic reaction like photosynthesis, protein synthesis while chemical reactions in which large molecule break down into simple molecules referred as anabolism like respiration, digestion. In living organism these chemical reactions are catalysed by specific enzymes. If activity of enzyme is inhibited, these reactions will also stop as result whole metabolic process will also inhibited.

Polyphenols could pass through the gastrointestinal system without being absorbed, thus affecting intestinal microbiota. This can lead to two consequences: first, polyphenols are modified into their active form; second, they change the composition of the intestinal microbiota, probably inhibiting pathogenic bacteria and enriching beneficial bacteria. Phenolic compound can also inhibit activity of enzyme.

Quinones are characterized by having an aromatic ring with two ketone substitutions. Quinone antimicrobial activity comes from their ability to donate free radicals. They can also form irreversible complexes with amino acids in proteins, thus inactivating them. These properties of quinones make it possible for them to attack surface adhesions, polypeptides in the cell wall, and membrane enzymes. Quinones may also sequester substrates required by the microorganisms.

Flavones consist of an aromatic ring with only one ketone substitution. Hydroxylation yields a flavonol. Flavonoids occur as a C3-C8 unit linked to a phenolic ring that is also hydroxylated. These compounds are known to be synthesized in plants as a defense mechanism against microorganisms; thus, their antimicrobial effect is of no surprise. Their antimicrobial properties are probably because they form complexes with both extracellular and soluble proteins, as well as bacterial cell wall. They could also disrupt cell membranes if lipophilic enough.

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Tannins are a group of polymeric phenolics. They are divided into two main categories: hydrolyzable and condensed tannins. Gallic acid forms the basis of hydrolyzable tannins, usually esterified at multiple locations with D-glucose. Condensed tannins are more abundant and are derived from flavonoid monomers; they may be referred to as proanthocyanidins. Tannins' biological activity could be correlated to the patterns of oxidation and polymerization (Coppo and Marchese, 2014). Tannins exert their antimicrobial effect by complexing with proteins through both covalent and non-covalent interactions. They are also capable of complexing with polysaccharides. Evidence also exists for direct inactivation of microorganisms.

It was shown that low concentrations of tannins changed the morphology of the gem tubes of *Crinipellis peniclosa*. In the case of condensed tannins, they have also been shown to be capable of binding cell walls of ruminal bacteria, inhibiting growth, and protease activity.

Alkaloids are heterocyclic structures containing one or more nitrogen atoms. There are two broad divisions in the classification according to the chemical structure. The first division contains the non-heterocyclic or atypical alkaloids, also called protoalkaloids or biological amines, such as hordenine or N-methyltyramine, colchicine, and erythromycin (an antibiotic; Evans, 2009). The second division includes the heterocyclic or typical alkaloids such as hygrines belonging to the pyrrole and pyrrolidine group, and quinine belonging to the quinoline group. They show different types of modes of action. Alkaloids can form hydrogen bonds with enzymes, receptors, and proteins, since they have, in addition to functional groups, a proton-accepting nitrogen atom, and one or even more proton-donating amine hydrogen atoms. Alkaloids have many pharmacological properties, such as central nervous system stimulants (brucine), anticholinergic agents (atropine), oxytocic and vasoconstrictor activity (ergometrine), and antimalarial activity. Antibacterial mechanisms of action differ between different alkaloids.

CONCEPT OF HEALTH AND DISEASE ACCORDING TO MICRO CELL PATHY

Human body is made of about 75 trillion cells that is 75, 000, 000, 000, 000 cells that number of body cell depends on the body size, the body cells are forming tissues. Tissues are forming organ, organs are forming systems and systems are forming the human body.

We all are facing today is not only the poor quality of foods but also the fact that we don't absorb enough nutrients and vitamins from foods and supplements environmental toxins are a fact of life, every time we breath, we are taking in airborne toxins, much of the processed food we eat contains artificial ingredients, such as color & preservatives that do nothing to nourish our body, most of body cells get covered with toxins and cannot absorb all the nutrients that they need to maintain our health, ideal weight and daily energy, in order to become healthier and stay healthy we need cellular nutrition that acts at the core of our body the cellular level.

Dr. P.K. Das developed a plant based new medical science MICRO CELL PATHY which is based on the most advanced cellular nutrition science, which is acting at the cellular level of our body. The human body needs 116 essential daily nutrients in order to function properly and maintain an optimal weight, energy and health as we age our body cells get tired or processing nutrients and get covered with toxins from foods, water and air, causing the metabolism to slow down, nothing it very heart for the body to process and absorb all the essential nutrients from foods, provided that all our meals.

MICRO CELL PATHY helps to clean the body cells of toxins and keep them active in order for the body to be able to absorb and process all the essential nutrients from foods and supplements.

Micro cell pathy can be only obtained through a special blend of highly organic and inorganic constituents of plants and strong antioxidants properties of plant that activate the body cells and help them absorb and process the essential daily nutrients and vitamins from food and supplements and fulfill the deficiency of organic and inorganic constituents.

Micro cell pathy is acting at the cellular level of our body the cellular level is the basic functional unit of our body and core of our body's health, which make up our entire body and allows our body to function by using organic and inorganic constitutions and antioxidants of plants these constituents cleaning of our body cells of toxins and then feeding our body at the

cellular level which is helping all our body cells to become active again.

Exercise also essential because our body needs to increase and maintain in its muscle in order to burn calories and achieve good health.

FUNDAMENTAL PRINCIPLE OF MICRO CELL PATHY

Micro Cell Pathy is an alternative system of medicine; Naturopath Dr. P K Das from India in 2017 founded it. Its practitioners called micro cell paths/ MCP practitioners/ Micro paths believe that deficiency of organic and inorganic constituents are responsible for abnormal function of cell and its metabolism, it leads to disease or degeneration treatment is same its organic and inorganic constituents are present in plants. According to law of transformation of energy and organic/ inorganic / micro and macro constituents present in plant. Disease body cell have losses all these organic and inorganic constituents micro cell pathy preparations are termed remedies and are made using micro cell pathy pills diluted in 120ml glass of water, in this process the selected pills/globules diluted in one glass of water (1 pill in 120ml of water) according to pathological conditions. Micro cell pathy treat diseased organs not only symptoms, practitioners are claim that such preparation and upon oral intake can treat or cure diseases.

BASIC PRINCIPLE OF MICRO CELL PATHY

Deficiency of organic and inorganic constituents/macro and micro trace elements are responsible for abnormal function of cell and its metabolism. It leads to diseases or degeneration, treatment is same it's functional constituents are present in plants in the form of organic and inorganic.

Organic Molecules	Inorganic Molecules
Nucleic acids	Silicon
Proteins	Sodium
Organic acids	Potassium
Carbohydrates	Nickel
Lipid	Mo
Fatty acids	Cu
& Secondary metabolites of plants	Zn
	Mn
	Fe
	& B are micro nutrients of plants
These elements are essential for growth and metabolic activity	

"MICRO CELL PATHY" WORKS ON 2 SCIENTIFIC LAW THAT IS LAW OF MASS ACTION AND LAW OF TRANSFORMATION OF ENERGY

Law of Mass action

(Law of mass action is the proposition that the rate of a chemical reaction is directly proportional to the product of the product of the activities or concentration of the reactant)

PROTOCOL OF "MICRO CELL PATHY"

1. Hydration (Dry plants dip in water for hydration of plants)
2. Extraction (Extract plants juices)
3. Infusion (Infusion with honey)
4. Calcination (Calcination residue part of plants for use of CT group)
5. Assimilation (Assimilation of organic and inorganic parts of plants)
6. Filtration (Filter of odic tincture according to MCP method)

1ST PROCESS OF EXTRACT MEDICINAL COMPUNDS FROM MEDICINAL PLANTS

Dry medicinal plants

Dip in water minimum 8 hours for hydration of plants

Extract juices

Keep in a glass container

1 Part of plant juice + 3 part of water + 1 part of honey

Keep in a dark room for 7 days

(Organic compounds) break down of complex substances into simple form primary metabolites (micronutrients) to secondary metabolites

MAKING OF GLOBULES REMEDY IN MCP

1 Part of DJ 5 Part of Rectified Sprit Stirrup the solution clockwise without stroke

When we stirrup the solution there is two forces are called cohesive force and Adhesive force

Adhesive and Cohesive forces are the intermolecular forces (such as those from hydrogen bonding and van der Waals forces) which cause a tendency in liquids to resist separation. These attractive forces exist between molecules of the same substance. For instance, rain falls in droplets, rather than a fine mist, because water has strong cohesion, which pulls its molecules tightly together, forming droplets. This force tends to unite molecules of a liquid, gathering them into relatively large clusters due to the molecules dislike for its surrounding.

Adhesive forces are the attractive forces between unlike molecules. Forces acting between two substances, such as mechanical forces (sticking together) and electrostatic forces (attraction due to opposing charges) cause them. In the case of liquid wetting agent, adhesion causes the liquids to cling to the surface on which it rests. When water is poured on clean glass, it tends to spread, forming a thin, uniform film over the glasses surface. This is because the adhesive forces between water and glass are strong enough to pull the water molecules out of their spherical formation and hold them against the surface of the glass, thus avoiding the repulsion between like molecules. Macroscopic effects of cohesive and adhesive forces when liquid is placed on a smooth surface, the relative strengths of the cohesive and adhesive forces acting on that liquid determine the shape it will take (and whether or not it will wet the surface). If the adhesive forces between a liquid and a surface are stronger, they will pull the liquid down, causing it to wet the surface. However, if they cohesive forces among the liquid itself are stronger, they will resist such adhesion and cause the liquid to retain a spherical shape and bead the surface.

1 Part of DJ

5 Part of Rectified Sprit = OT1

1 Part of OT1 + Part of RS = OT2

1Part of OT2 + 5 Part of RS = OT3

Now OT3 is ready to making globules

MCP PILLS USING METHOD

Conditions and Disease Progression Chart By Dr. P. K. Das

ETIOLOGY OF DISEASE IT'S CONDITION, NOMENCLATUER, DOSOLOGY AND DILUATION

IN MICRO CELL PATHY CAUSES OF DISEASE IS DUE TO DYSFUNCTION OR DISTURBANCE OF CELL & IT'S METABOLISM

“DYSFUNCTION OR DISTRUBANCE OF CELL & CELLULAR METABOLISM”

PRODUCE MORBID CONDITIONS IN CELLS / TISSUES / ORGANS

CONDITIONS ARE HYPO OR HYPER (-Ve) OR (+Ve)

DUE TO HYPO AND HYPER CONDITION OF ORGAN 7 PATHOLOGICAL STAGES

ARE DEVELOP

THESE ARE

When function of cell is disturbed or disturbance on its metabolic pathway it lead to disease or degeneration & chance to develop seven pathological conditions.

1st condition STAGNATION is appear. 2nd INFLAMATION. 3rd PAIN & NUMNESS. 4th FEVER. 5th SUPPERATION due to suppuratation degeneration of cells is appear. Later it increase in Gangrene and cancer.